

ROLE OF LOCAL TH2-INFLAMMATION OF THE NASAL MUCOSA IN THE FORMATION OF SEPTOPLASTY RESULTS

Umarov Bakhtiyor Yatgarovich

Otayev Hamid Sultanovich

Director of the Children's National Medical
Center, DSc, Associate professor
Plastic surgeon of the Medmemorial Hospital clinic,
Urgench, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19563628>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09th April 2026

Accepted: 11th April 2026

Online: 13th April 2026

KEYWORDS

septoplasty, *Th2-link,*
inflammation, *preoperative*
period, *functional outcomes,*
nasal respiration

ABSTRACT

Traditionally, poor outcomes of septoplasty are associated with technical aspects of the operation or anatomical features of the nasal cavity, but in recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the role of inflammatory and immunological factors that can modify postoperative recovery. Of particular interest is allergic inflammation of the nasal mucosa associated with allergic rhinitis, which is characterized by activation of the Th2-link of immunity, hyperproduction of immunoglobulin E and eosinophilic tissue infiltration.

Introduction.

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in comprehensive assessment of the clinical characteristics of patients undergoing septoplasty, using both subjective methods, including the NOSE scale and visual-analog scale, and objective research methods, such as nasal endoscopy[1,3]. This approach makes it possible to more accurately assess the effectiveness of surgical treatment and identify factors associated with favorable and unfavorable outcomes[2].

Materials and methods. The study was conducted with the participation of 160 patients with nasal septal deformity and nasal breathing disorders who underwent examination and surgical treatment in the period from 2022 to 2025. Depending on the chronology of work stages, patients were divided into two groups:

- the control group consisted of 78 (48.8%) patients who underwent standard methods of diagnosis and surgical treatment during 2022-2023 with parallel determination of allergological and immunological parameters without changing the standard management tactics;

- the main group consisted of 82 (51.2%) patients who, in the period from 2024-2025, used the methods developed by us for predicting and preventing adverse functional outcomes according to the treatment and diagnostic algorithm developed by us.

Results. In the early postoperative period, intergroup differences persisted. In patients with an unsatisfactory outcome, the total IgE level remained almost 2.8 times higher than in those with a favorable outcome ($p < 0.001$), and local eosinophilia remained more than 3 times

higher ($p < 0.001$). The most pronounced differences were related to mucosal inflammation, which was confirmed by a significant increase in eosinophils in nasal cytology and ENI index.

Conclusion. Thus, the analysis demonstrates that the severity of Th2-mediated immune response, especially at the local level, is closely related to the functional results of septoplasty. At the same time, mucosal eosinophilic infiltration is a key marker of an unfavorable outcome, reflecting the degree of persistent inflammation of the nasal mucosa.

References:

1. Inan M.I., Akgul Balaban Y., Demirel F. et al. Tracking systemic inflammation in allergic rhinitis with immune-inflammation markers // *International Archives of Allergy and Immunology*. - 2025. - P. 1-8.
2. Izmailovich M. R., Gazalieva M. A., Glushkova N.E. et al. Eosinophilic cationic protein in patients with allergic rhinitis. - 2020. - Vol. 22, No. 1. - pp. 39-47.
3. Karpishchenko S. A., Vereshchagina O. E., Baranskaya S. V. et al. Revision septum operation / *Folia Otorhinolaryngologiae et Pathologiae Respiratoriae*. - 2021. - Vol. 27, No. 2. - pp. 13-21.